

HEADACHE AND HYPOTHYROIDISM

Scientific supervisor: **Davranova Aziza Davranovna**

Assistant of the Department of Endocrinology, Samarkand State Medical University

¹ **Yusupov Mehroj Sattor ugli**, ² **Subhonova Zarnigor Sultonbek kizi**,

³ **Sangirova Fotima Abdirahmon kizi**

^{1,2} Students of group 418 of the Faculty of pediatric, Samarkand State Medical University

³ Student of group 408 of the Faculty of Medicine, Samarkand State Medical University

Annotation. Hypothyroidism usually manifests itself with a wide range of symptoms from various body systems, including the nervous system. It has been established that approximately 30% of patients with reduced thyroid function suffer from headaches (HT), which are associated with a deficiency of thyroid hormones. Both primary and secondary hypothyroidism can not only lead to secondary headache, but also aggravate pre-existing primary headache, most often migraine. It is known that headache is more common in women, especially with a history of migraine. In everyday clinical practice, hypertension associated with hypothyroidism is rarely diagnosed as an independent form of secondary hypertension. More often, primary headaches, such as migraine and tension-type headaches, are regarded as concomitant diseases in patients with reduced thyroid function. To date, data on the relationship between hypothyroidism and migraine, as well as hypothyroidism and tension headaches, are contradictory, and it is not always possible to establish which process is primary and which is secondary. The pathophysiological basis explaining the relationship between hypothyroidism and headache/migraine is still not understood.

Keywords: hypothyroidism, headache, migraine, tension headache, thyroid-stimulating hormone, hypothalamus, levothyroxine, Hashimoto's thyroiditis, Hashimoto's encephalopathy, migraine preventive therapy.

Introduction. Hypothyroidism is a disease characterized by a decrease in the amount of thyroid hormones. Primary acquired hypothyroidism accounts for approximately 99% of all cases of hypothyroidism and is one of the most common endocrine diseases. According to the results of the large population-based study NHANES-III [1], its prevalence is 4.6% (0.3% manifest, 4.3% subclinical)1. According to the American

Thyroid Association for the Treatment of Hypothyroidism [2, 3], approximately 12% of the adult population is diagnosed with subclinical hypothyroidism, and among older people - 10% [4]. Clinical manifestations of hypothyroidism are nonspecific [5]. The most common symptoms are severe fatigue, drowsiness, chilliness, dry skin, hair loss, slow speech, swelling of the face, fingers and toes, constipation, memory loss, hoarseness and depressed mood¹. In a population-based case-control study [6], the most common symptoms reported in patients with hypothyroidism were fatigue (81%), dry skin (63%), and shortness of breath (51%). Among the 34 symptoms studied, only 13 were statistically significantly more common in hypothyroidism, and none of them turned out to be specific or sufficient to decide on the need to evaluate thyroid function [6]. The relationship between hypothyroidism and headaches (HT) has been known for more than 60 years [7, 8]. Although both physicians and patients often do not associate hypertension with hypothyroidism, it is perhaps one of the most common clinical manifestations of thyroid hormone deficiency and occurs in approximately a third of patients [8–11]. Primary and secondary hypothyroidism can lead to both the development of secondary headache and aggravate pre-existing primary headache, most often migraine. Data from epidemiological studies indicate that primary hypertension and hypothyroidism are comorbid diseases, between which there is a bidirectional relationship [12]. However, in a retrospective study by I. Spanou et al. [13] no specific association was found between primary headache subtypes and specific thyroid disease. However, among patients with primary hypertension, a high prevalence of thyroid dysfunction in general and hypothyroidism in particular has been demonstrated [13].

Headache associated with hypothyroidism. According to the third edition of the International Classification of Headache Disorders ICHD-3, headache associated with hypothyroidism is classified in the section “Headaches associated with disturbances of homeostasis” [14]. This is a bilateral, non-pulsatile headache that decreases after normalization of thyroid hormone levels.

Diagnostic criteria for hypertension associated with hypothyroidism [14]:

- A. GB meeting criterion C.
- B. Hypothyroidism is diagnosed.
- C. Evidence of causation is demonstrated by at least two of the following **characteristics:**

Hypertension develops in close temporal connection with the onset of hypothyroidism or led to its diagnosis;

one or both of the following conditions are met:

- a) Hypertension increases significantly along with the worsening of hypothyroidism;

b) headache significantly decreases or stops simultaneously with improvement or resolution of hypothyroidism;

GB has one or both of the following characteristics:

a) two-way localization;

b) constant.

D. Does not meet another ICHD-3 diagnosis.

In the presented diagnostic criteria, the description of headache is limited to only two characteristics: persistence and bilateral localization of pain.

In a study by T. Moreau et al. [10] showed that patients with hypothyroidism, as a rule, experience constant hypertension of low intensity, non-pulsating nature and bilateral localization, which disappears with the start of hormone replacement therapy for the underlying disease. It is also noted that this variant of headache is never accompanied by nausea or vomiting. However, in a study by L. Carvalho et al. [15] showed that patients with hypothyroidism may also experience episodic unilateral pulsating headache of moderate or high intensity, accompanied by nausea and/or vomiting. The above characteristics of headache meet the diagnostic criteria for migraine. If the patient had no history of migraines before the development of hypothyroidism, then such headache with a migraine phenotype should be regarded as secondary, associated with hypothyroidism. A study [10] showed that the intensity and duration of headache caused by hypothyroidism decreased within 2 weeks. after initiation of treatment with levothyroxine sodium in 58% and headache completely resolved in 42% of patients over the next 12 months. observations. The vast majority of patients with hypothyroidism within the first 2 months. When taking thyroid replacement therapy, a decrease in headache intensity was noted [15]. The reason why not all patients with hypothyroidism develop hypertension remains unknown. Currently available studies have not found factors associated with the occurrence of hypertension in hypothyroidism (gender, age, primary or secondary variant of the disease, level of thyroid hormones, the presence of arterial hypertension, obesity, etc.) [15].

Migraine and hypothyroidism. It has been established that the prevalence of hypothyroidism in patients with primary hypertension is higher than in the general population [16]. However, a number of researchers consider only migraine and hypothyroidism to be comorbid diseases [17]. According to the literature, decreased thyroid function in patients with migraine is observed in 3% of cases [16]. On the other hand, the development of hypothyroidism in patients with migraine can lead to a change in its course and transition from episodic to chronic. Among patients with chronic migraine, hypothyroidism is 8.4 times more common than among patients with an episodic form of the disease. Thus, hypothyroidism may be a risk factor for chronic hypertension [18, 19]. However, with the development of chronic daily headache in

patients with hypothyroidism, the question always remains open: are we seeing an increase in migraine attacks against the background of hormonal dysfunction or is this the debut of headache caused by hypothyroidism? In cases where headache is one of the symptoms of hypothyroidism, a positive response to therapy with levothyroxine sodium can be expected and preventive treatment for migraine may not be necessary. It has been shown that when the level of thyroid-stimulating hormone (TSH) is normalized during treatment with levothyroxine sodium, a decrease in the severity and frequency of migraine attacks is observed [15, 20]. However, it is known that a third of patients with hypertension do not respond to thyroid replacement therapy. In this regard, the following tactics are proposed: if headache persists after 3 months. treatment of hypothyroidism, it is recommended to use a combination of levothyroxine sodium with drugs for the preventive treatment of migraine (drugs from the group of β -blockers, antiepileptic drugs, antidepressants, monoclonal antibodies to calcitonin gene-related peptide (CGRP) or its receptor, botulinum toxin type A).

Pathogenesis of headache development in hypothyroidism. The mechanisms explaining the occurrence of hypertension in patients with hypothyroidism have not been sufficiently studied. Several such mechanisms have been proposed, including unidirectional or bidirectional causal relationships between hypertension and hypothyroidism, shared genetic factors, and environmental factors. The nature of the close relationship between migraine and thyroid dysfunction also remains unclear: a number of researchers [18, 21] suggest that migraine increases the risk of developing thyroid dysfunction, while other studies have not found such a relationship [15, 22]. In the last decade, active study of the genetic factors underlying the comorbidity of migraine and hypothyroidism has continued. Possible candidate genes responsible for the risk of developing both migraine and autoimmune thyroid disease have been identified [13, 14]. Most of the genes involved in the development of these diseases are associated with dysregulation of the immune system [15]. It has been demonstrated that the production of thyroid hormones and the regulation of the immune system are interrelated [16]. Currently, a hypothesis has been presented about the role of the hypothalamus in the formation of comorbid relationships between migraine and thyroid dysfunction. The development of a migraine attack is associated with dysfunction of the hypothalamus and limbic system, and neuroendocrine changes in the hypothalamus that occur during an attack naturally lead to changes in the level of hormones, in particular TSH, testosterone and growth hormone. Pain impulses received by the hypothalamus during a migraine attack may increase or decrease the levels of TSH and free thyroxine (depending on the individual setting of the hypothalamic-pituitary-thyroid axis), leading to dysfunction of the thyroid gland [16]. These pathophysiological mechanisms likely underlie the association between migraine and

hypothyroidism, both primary and secondary, the latter being biological pleiotropy rather than causation. Basic research conducted in recent decades has confirmed that CGRP plays a key role in the pathophysiology of migraine. On the other hand, it has been shown that the level of CGRP is increased in diseases of the thyroid gland (with the development of both hypothyroidism and hyperthyroidism) [17], which, in turn, increases the “susceptibility” of patients to migraine attacks [18]. Patients with primary hypothyroidism are deficient in calcitonin [19], but the role of calcitonin and its interaction with the CGRP system in migraine is unknown [20]. One study [21] reported chronicity of migraine in hypothyroid patients taking levothyroxine sodium due to possible insufficient secretion of calcitonin.

Headache and hyperprolactinemia. Patients with hypothyroidism may experience a secondary increase in prolactin levels [22]. The possible involvement of this hormone and its receptors in the pathophysiology of migraine has now been demonstrated in several clinical studies [21]. It has been suggested that elevated prolactin levels contribute to the chronicity and progression of the disease [19]. It is known that prolactin is expressed on CGRP-immunopositive sensory fibers and promotes the release of CGRP [20], in particular, in vitro experimental studies have demonstrated that prolactin enhances the release of CGRP. Thus, high levels of this hormone through the CGRP system can increase the sensitivity of sensory neurons and, accordingly, increase the likelihood of developing another migraine attack [21]. Clinical studies have demonstrated a decrease in the severity and frequency of headaches with normalization of prolactin levels [22,23]. It should be noted that migraine-like headache associated with hyperprolactinemia often does not respond to preventive therapy with drugs with proven effectiveness and decreases only after normalization of prolactin levels [24]. On the other hand, some drugs used in the treatment of migraine can affect prolactin levels [25], in particular, acetaminophen, triptans and propranolol reduce its content, while the use of valproic acid, on the contrary, leads to an increase in its level [28].

Headache due to Hashimoto's encephalopathy. Hashimoto's thyroiditis is the most common disease leading to primary hypothyroidism in children and adults [27]. This pathology is characterized by the presence of antithyroid antibodies, which can become a pathogenetic cause of the development of Hashimoto's encephalopathy (HEC) [26]. Hashimoto's encephalopathy is a rare autoimmune neurological disorder with extremely polymorphic clinical manifestations that is poorly diagnosed in clinical practice. Severe headache develops at the onset of the disease in 80% of cases, along with sleep disturbances, depression and apathy, but it is not the main complaint of patients with EC, as it is overshadowed by more pronounced affective, cognitive or neurological symptoms [29]. Since glucocorticoids are effective in patients with EC

with high concentrations of antithyroid antibodies [30], the syndrome is also called Steroid-Responsive Encephalopathy Associated with Autoimmune Thyroiditis (SREAT) [30-31]. The pathogenesis of EC has not yet been studied. It is assumed that its development is based on cerebral autoimmune inflammation due to cross-damage of the brain by antithyroid antibodies [32-33]. It is hypothesized that antibodies initially directed against the thyroid gland cross the blood-brain barrier into the brain parenchyma, causing an autoimmune lymphocytic response based on shared antigens between the brain and the thyroid gland. Other possible causes of EC include: isolated central nervous system vasculitis due to immune complex precipitation, pandysautonomia, demyelination, intrathecal synthesis of thyroid antibodies, global hypoperfusion, low cerebrospinal fluid hypocretin 1 (in cases of hypersomnolence or coma), and changes in the estrogen/progesterone ratio. in the luteal phase in women with exacerbations associated with the menstrual cycle [34]. Taking into account the relatively rare occurrence of the disease (2.1 cases per 100,000 adults [35]) and insufficiently studied pathogenesis, special studies on the treatment of hypertension in patients with EC have not been conducted. Glucocorticoids are indicated for most patients with EC; their use can reduce the severity of headache.

Conclusion. Hypothyroidism can lead to the development of secondary headache and aggravate the course of pre-existing primary headache, in particular migraine. Hypothyroidism-associated headache may have a mixed phenotype, with clinical features of tension-type headache and migraine not meeting diagnostic criteria for primary headache. Current guidelines do not recommend routine TSH testing in hypertension, but it may be worth assessing TSH levels in patients with chronic hypertension if there are additional complaints of fatigue, cognitive and mental impairment. If hypothyroidism is detected in a patient with hypertension, it is necessary to initiate thyroid replacement therapy with levothyroxine sodium. If hypertension persists against the background of compensation for hypothyroidism, drugs for the preventive treatment of migraine should be added to treatment.

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